

RUSSIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES
INSTITUTE OF TERRESTRIAL MAGNETISM,
IONOSPHERE AND
RADIOWAVE PROPAGATION

Preprint of IZMIRAN No. 21 (1071)

Lyubimov V.V.

**PRELIMINARY RESULTS OF THE
MAGNETOMETRIC RESEARCHES
IN 7-th CRUISE OF THE R/V "ACADEMIK NIKOLAY
STRAKHOV"
IN CENTRAL AND EQUATORIAL PART OF THE
ATLANTIC OCEAN**

The material of this work was reported during
Indo-Russian Symposium on "Nature and Variations
of the Geomagnetic Field", 2 - 6 February 1993,
New Delhi, India.

Moscow 1994

УДК 550.380.

Lyubimov V.V. Preliminary results of the magnetometric researches in 7-th cruise of the r/v "Academik Nikolay Strakhov" in central and equatorial part of the Atlantic Ocean. Preprint No.21 (1071), Moscow: IZMIRAN, 1994. - 35 p.

Preliminary results of the magnetometric researches in 7-th cruise of the research vessel "Academik Nikolay Strakhov" are given in paper.

Magnetic survey in equatorial part of Atlantic Ocean (in area from 1 N till 4 N) can divide on beams magnetic survey and survey on magnetic grounds. The fundamental part of magnetic survey was made in magnetic equator's region where inclination of magnetic field force vector was within the limits ± 10 angle degrees.

Magnetic survey on grounds was included of the three main regions: Petropavlovsky ridge, San-Poul's and Strakhov's fracture zones where neighbouring tacks distance was from 2,5 till 5 miles.

As a result of magnetic survey were made the anomalous magnetic field maps for magnetic grounds which are given in paper too.

C IZMIRAN, 1994 г.